

THE ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF COCOA INDUSTRY IN COUNTRIES OF THE GULF OF GUINEA

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Abstract

Global chocolate production is a multibillion-dollar industry, with Africa producing more than 75% of the world's cocoa crop. Aside from Benin, every country in the Gulf of Guinea grows cocoa trees. Ghana and the Ivory Coast are the two largest producers, followed by Nigeria and Cameroon.

Cocoa is commercially significant for both gulf African producing countries and western consuming countries. This article initially discusses the global cocoa value chain before delving into cocoa production in the major cocoa-growing countries in the gulf of Guinea. Finally, the cocoa industry's significance to the economic progress of Gulf of Guinea countries is discussed. The author used a qualitative technique with secondary data sources to assess the cocoa business and its relevance in gulf African countries in this research study. The author finds that the cocoa sector is critical to the economies of the gulf African countries. However, value-added activities like as grinding and processing are primarily found in Europe.

Keywords: Cocoa, Africa, Industry, Gulf countries, Economy.

INTRODUCTION

The dried and fully fermented fatty seed of *Theobroma cacao*, from which cocoa solids and cocoa oil are derived, is known as the cocoa bean, or simply cocoa. The "beans" are the key component of chocolate and items made with cacao. Products made from cocoa beans are utilized in a variety of food products in addition to chocolates. Over five million tons of cocoa are anticipated to be produced worldwide in the 2022–2023 crop year. The cost of a kilogram of cocoa remains well over two dollars in recent years.

The Americas are home to the cocoa tree. Its original origins are in regions of Mexico and Central America. The cocoa industry developed over time to become an essential component of numerous cultures. Cocoa is typically grown in tropical and subtropical climates. It is highly vulnerable to pests and diseases and is very selective to soil and climate. Throughout the industry's growth, when cocoa was grown for markets in temperate nations, this regional exactitude had a huge impact on worldwide cocoa consumption and marketing.

Cocoa production has had a major role in shaping the economic, social, and political structures of cocoa-producing countries since its discovery. Not only has it done so on a local level, but it has also defined the role of producing countries in the global economy. Today, Africa contributes for about 75.2 percent of global cacao production, Asia accounts for 5.7%, and Latin America accounts for 19.2%. The largest producing country in terms of capacity is Ivory Coast, which produces 33% of the world's supply. Africa's leading producers are Ivory Coast, Ghana, Nigeria, and Cameroon; Asia's leading producers are Indonesia, Malaysia, and Papua New Guinea; while the Americas' leading producers are Brazil, Ecuador, and Columbia, in that order.

Over 80-90% of cocoa production is produced by small, family-run farms, with an estimated 5 to 6 million cocoa growers worldwide. Cocoa production increased by 13% between 2008 and 2012. Between 2008 and 2012, it increased from 4.3 million to 4.8 million metric tons. In 2021/2022, Africa's cocoa bean production was anticipated to reach over 3.6 million metric tons, with the Ivory Coast producing more than half of that, approximately 2.1 million tons. Europe and the United States, being the most prominent chocolate-producing countries, are major importers of post-processable cocoa products. The paper first examines the global cocoa value chain before delving into cocoa production in the major cocoa-growing countries in the gulf of Guinea. Finally, the cocoa industry's significance to the economic progress of Gulf of Guinea countries is discussed.

THE GLOBAL COCOA VALUE CHAIN

The cocoa value chain begins with the fruit of the tropical cacao, or cocoa tree. Farmers within 25 degrees of the equator grow cocoa, frequently as part of a mix of seasonal crops, and harvest the fruits weekly. In West Africa, where the majority of the world's cacao is cultivated, the cocoa value chain frequently runs from farmers to intermediaries collectors to local purchasers (in some circumstances, the government) to local processors or huge multinational buyers who distribute it to chocolate makers and cosmetics companies[11].

The majority of cocoa beans sent abroad are purchased by foreign wholesalers through the global cocoa market. Buyers keep the beans in warehouses, the largest of which are located in New York and Amsterdam, and then distribute cocoa regionally from there. Cocoa can be stored in warehouses for months before being sold. When it reaches a chocolate factory, it undergoes

a lengthy procedure to become the product we know and love.

Some of the large corporations involved in the worldwide cocoa-chocolate value chain expand their activity in both markets, producers, and consumers. Simultaneously, they operate in consumer markets, controlling high-value activities originating from the industrial manufacture of chocolate to branding, and in intermediate markets, dominating the global supply chain for cocoa raw materials to consuming countries [1]. According to the author, the five consumer market leaders (Mondelez International, Mars Inc., Nestlé, Ferrero, and Hershey Co.) own well-known brands. They handle high-value functions linked to chocolate manufacturing as well as the development and marketing of brands with significant purchasing and negotiation power [1]. Three of the world's biggest firms control global supply chains; vertically integrated, they operate from rural areas of producing countries to major ports in Europe and North America, where advanced processing facilities are located. Vertically integrated supply chains such as Barry Callebaut, Cargill, and ADM control about half of all processed cocoa worldwide.

As a result, there has been a shift toward more directly sourced cocoa, so shortening the cocoa value chain from farmers to wholesalers to factories. This reduces the transit time for cocoa and allows more of the

final cost of cocoa to be returned to the farmers, emphasizing the importance of cocoa quality over quantity. Buying cocoa directly from farmers is a hallmark of the craft chocolate movement, which aspires to make the cocoa value chain more transparent and advantageous to all participants.

The basis and transmission of pricing along the cocoa-chocolate value chain is explained by the asymmetry in power relations along the chain. In general, retail prices rise as cocoa bean prices rise, but they fall more slowly when cocoa bean prices fall. As a result, the reduction in cocoa bean prices has varying effects for the various points in the chain. It will have an immediate and severe impact on farmers' incomes, while the rest of the value chain actors can boost their profit margins, albeit briefly [10].

Over the last 40 years, cocoa production has continuously expanded, with up to 95% of cocoa beans traded on international commodities markets. The cocoa market is dynamic, with several trends and variations. Political concerns, weather-related production deficits, and overproduction in producing countries, among other things, cause the ups and downs. The graph below depicts the global production of cocoa beans by region. As stated above, although chocolate is primarily manufactured in Europe and North America, cacao is primarily grown in Africa, Central and South America, and the Caribbean.

Production of cocoa beans worldwide from 2003/2004 to 2021/2022, by region (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

As mentioned earlier, West Africa produces roughly two-thirds of the world's cocoa beans, with Ivory Coast and Ghana being the two largest producers.

Together, these two countries produce half of the world's cocoa [7]. The graph below depicts global cocoa output by country.

Global cocoa bean production from 2020/21 to 2022/23, by country (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

The following largest cocoa producing countries, in order, are Ecuador, Cameroon, Nigeria, Indonesia, Brazil, Papua New Guinea. Indonesia hardly grew cocoa before 1980 but is now one of the biggest cocoa producing country in the world [22]. Currently, Asia produces about 13% of the world's cocoa beans, but this is only going to increase. There are now many countries in Asia producing cocoa including India, Malaysia, Vietnam, Philippines, and Thailand. It is a fairly new crop to this region but they are becoming increasingly important areas for cultivating cocoa.

Cocoa came in Asia for the first time in the 17th century, in the Philippines, during the Spanish colonial period. According to the 1877 folio Flora De Filipinas, "cacao first traveled outside its American homeland in 1670 from Acapulco, Mexico to the Philippines aboard Manila galleons." It subsequently expanded to other parts of Southeast Asia over the next couple of centuries.

When it comes to the origins of cocoa in Thailand, the seeds most likely arrived from Malaysia in the early twentieth century and have since been grown. It is not a major crop in Thailand, but it is still produced in places like Chantaburi, Chiang Mai, Chumphon, Koh Samui, Nong Khai, and I'm sure many others. This is quite surprising given that Chiang Mai is located 18 degrees north of the equator. Unfortunately, according to reportlinker.com, Thailand's yearly cocoa production

has decreased from 932.00 tonnes in 2007 to only 117.00 tonnes in 2016.

Roughly 15% of the world's cocoa beans are still grown in South and Central America, where cocoa originated. Up until the Ivory Coast and West Africa surpassed Brazil as the world's top producers of cocoa in the 19th century, Brazil was the world's largest producer of cocoa. With 235.809 tonnes produced, they continue to be the largest producer on the American continent, followed closely by Ecuador with 205,955 tonnes. Moreover, Mexico, Peru, Colombia, and the Dominican Republic grow cocoa. Given that West Africa is running out of land on which to grow cocoa and that their yields per hectare are lower than those of Malaysia, Asia has the ability to grow and contribute to meeting the growing demand for cocoa around the world.

The monthly price of cocoa worldwide between 2016 and 2023 peaked in the middle of 2016 at roughly 3,122 dollars per metric ton and has since varied between about 1,900 and 2,700 dollars per metric ton[13]. The last price low was achieved in 2016–2017 as a result of a record-breaking harvest, which sent prices plummeting to their lowest point in a decade. Prices have been gradually increasing ever since [7]. The price of cocoa worldwide from 2008 to 2022 is depicted in the picture below.

World cocoa price from 2008 to 2022 (in U.S. dollars per kilogram)

Source: Statista 2023

The world's biggest importer of cocoa beans is the Netherlands. The Netherlands imported 895 thousand tons in 2020. This accounts for 24% of all imports of cocoa beans worldwide. Between 2016 and 2020, the Netherlands' overall import volume of cocoa beans increased at an average annual rate of 2.3%. The COVID-19 epidemic and disruptions in the global supply chain resulted in decreased amounts of cocoa bean imports by the Netherlands in 2020, albeit they were still marginally higher than in 2016.

Approximately 140,000 tons of cocoa and cocoa-related products were imported in 2021; the majority of these products were cocoa beans and cocoa butter. This is comparable to about 120,000 tons of cocoa bean equivalents being imported. The total of all imported cocoa goods (such as cocoa butter, cocoa powder, etc.)

transformed into cocoa beans using the conversion factors established by the International Cocoa Organization (ICCO) is referred to as cocoa bean equivalents. Cocoa butter 1.33, cocoa paste/liquor 1.25, cocoa powder and cocoa cake 1.18, chocolate and chocolate goods 0.40, and chocolate products classified as containing only half the typical proportion of cocoa 0.20 are the conversion factors used to determine the bean equivalent of cocoa products. In the form of semi-finished or finished goods, very little is imported. Equivalents of cocoa beans are mostly exported as cocoa paste and unfilled chocolate. Ninety-nine percent of the cocoa beans imported into the Netherlands came straight from the producing nations. Ghana and Ecuador are the two biggest importers of cocoa beans into the Netherlands. The top international importers of cocoa are depicted in the figure below.

Leading cocoa bean importers worldwide in 2022 (in million U.S. dollars)

Source: Statista 2023

The port of Amsterdam, the world's largest cocoa port, is where cocoa beans enter the Netherlands. The port boasts substantial and well-equipped import, storage, and cocoa processing facilities, and the area is home to several cocoa value chain actors. Because of the port's and region's experience, concentration of facilities and actors, focus on sustainability, and flexibility to innovate, the Netherlands is projected to continue to play a key role in the cocoa trade. In the Netherlands,

companies that specialize in cocoa bean storage include Commodity Centre Netherlands, CJ Hendriks Group, and C. Steinweg Group.

The primary cocoa bean processing region is Europe. Worldwide, cocoa beans are processed to create chocolate, cocoa butter, cocoa powder, cocoa mass, and other cocoa-based products. In Europe, one-third of the yearly harvest is ground. The top cocoa processors by region are displayed in the figure below.

Global leading processor of cocoa beans

Nearly 710,000 tons of cocoa beans were processed in Côte d'Ivoire in 2021–2022, according to the data. The Netherlands boasts the second-largest cocoa-

grinding sector globally, following Ivory Coast. In addition to providing an estimate for 2022–2023, the figure below shows the top processing nations for cocoa beans globally in 2021–2022.

Global cocoa bean production from 2020/21 to 2022/23, by country (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

An estimated 600,000 tonnes of cocoa beans were consumed by the Dutch cocoa-grinding industry in 2020 and 2021. The Netherlands' cocoa-grinding operations stayed steady between 2018 and 2020. But by 2021, the COVID-19 pandemic's consequences on the cocoa-grinding businesses became apparent. According to a report by the European Cocoa Organisation (ECA), there was a decline in the volume of cocoa grinding throughout Europe in the first quarter of 2021 but in the year 2023 there was an increase compared to the previous year's [9]. Nevertheless, Rabobank analysis [6] indicated that there was still hope for the cocoa-grinding industry's overall revival.

Strong retail sales across Europe are likely to propel the Dutch cocoa-grinding industry's steady recovery to grinding volumes. The Netherlands' cocoa grinding industry is facing competition from growing cocoa-

grinding operations at origin, mostly in the Ivory Coast. Large international corporations (such as Cargill, Olam, and Barry Callebaut) control a significant portion of the grinding market at origin as a cost-cutting measure.

The cocoa grinding industry in the Netherlands is situated close to the Amsterdam port. It is home to both Dutch businesses like Dutch Cocoa, Daarnhouwer, and Theobroma (ECOM Group) and multinationals like Olam and Cargill. These businesses are crucial to the production and import of derivatives made from cocoa.

There is a significant global disparity in chocolate consumption, per Statista Market Insights [2]. Many individuals in Asia prefer other sugary treats to satiate their sweet taste, even though the cocoa-based dessert is highly popular in vast portions of Europe and the United States. The largest chocolate consumers worldwide are broken down by nation in the figure below.

The World's Biggest Chocolate Consumers

Source: Statista 2023

Switzerland leads the world in terms of chocolate consumption, with an astounding 11.8 kilos consumed annually per person in 2022. Toblerone and Lindt are two of the most well-known brands in the nation's great chocolate industry. With 5.8 kilograms per person, neighbouring Germany is ranked highly on the list, whilst Americans are thought to consume 9 kilograms of chocolate year on average. On the other end of the spectrum, Statista reports that China and India have significantly lower per-capita consumption, at 0.2 and 1.0 kg, respectively [12].

Africa has remained isolated from the consumption of various cocoa by products, such as chocolate, despite holding a leading position in the world's production of cocoa—it has been the world's primary source of cocoa beans for the majority of the 20th century [21]. However, since the year 2000, there has been a significant increase in both the consumption of chocolate and Africa's share of cocoa processing. The two world's fastest-growing chocolate markets, China and India, have growth rates for chocolate consumption that are similar to those of African nations. According to Tamru, Seneshaw, and Johan Swinnen (2016), this is brought on by the continent's remarkable increase in

economic growth, rising urbanization, the growth of contemporary retail stores, and a potential shift in taste toward more Westernized tastes.

PRODUCTION IN THE MAIN COCOA GROWING GULF AFRICAN COUNTRIES

About 20 million people in West Africa depend on cocoa as a primary source of income, and the crop generates substantial export money for the countries that grow it. Approximately 75% of the world's cocoa comes from Africa, according to the International Cocoa Organization (ICCO)[14].

The Western region of Africa produces almost all of the world's cocoa, mostly from Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire, which together account for 62% of the world's total production. Four of the top five cocoa producers are typically from the region; Nigeria and Cameroon, with respective shares of 7% and 8% of the world market, are ranked fourth and fifth. Smaller yields are also contributed by other nations in the region, such as Liberia, which is turning more and more to cash crops like cocoa to revive its economy. The graph below shows the yearly production of cocoa in Africa, broken down by nation, from 2018/2019 to 2022/2023.

Annual cocoa production of Africa from 2018/2019 to 2022/2023, by country (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

With slightly more than 2.12 million metric tons of cocoa produced that year, the Ivory Coast was the top producer, according to the report. According to the International Cocoa Organization's (ICCO) most recent Cocoa Market Report, Ghana outproduced Ivory Coast

in terms of cocoa production during the first half of the 2022–2023 crop season. The cocoa production in Ghana from 2012/2013 to 2022/2023 is depicted in the diagram below.

Production of cocoa beans in Ghana (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

As of March 31, 2023, Ivory Coast's cumulative arrivals of cocoa beans were falling short of previous season levels. Meanwhile, Ghana has purchased 566,846 tonnes of graded and sealed cocoa beans since the 2022–2023 season began, an 18% increase over the previous year. The combined supply of cocoa beans from the top two producers in the world for the first half of 2022–2023 is anticipated to be 2,345,846 tonnes, a little decrease of 0.2 percent from the previous season despite Ghana's increased cocoa production.

Furthermore, Ghana's Cocoa Processing Company Limited (CPC) reported revenue of 23.9 million US dollars for the first quarter of 2022. The processing factory's revenue generation increased overall between

2016 and 2021, reaching a peak of 41.84 million US dollars in 2021. CPC produces cocoa products like powder and bars by processing raw cocoa beans into semi-finished goods [19].

According to the ICCO report, there was a slight negative net effect during the first half of the 2022–2023 cocoa year due to the Ivory Coast's cumulative port arrivals of 89,000 tonnes fewer than the previous year, and Ghana's purchases of graded and sealed cocoa beans increased by 85,360 tonnes during the same period [14]. The cocoa production in Ivory Coast from 2012/2013 to 2022/2023 is depicted in the graphic below.

Production of cocoa beans in Ivory Coast (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

The report also mentioned that as the mid-crop develops, the current state of play could alter. But as of right now, Ghana is producing more cocoa than Ivory Coast, which is a big development for the world's cocoa market. Given that Ivory Coast has been the world's

leading producer of cocoa for a number of years, observers covering the cocoa market have characterized this move as historic. Nonetheless, this indicates that Ghana is making progress in raising the quantity and quality of its cocoa production, which is positive for the economy of the nation[4].

A number of measures, such as the adoption of contemporary farming methods, improved access to financing and markets, and increased infrastructural investment, have helped to raise Ghana's cocoa production recently. The Cocoa Health and Extension Division of the Ghana Cocoa Board (COCOBOD) is one such project that offers farmers free seedlings, subsidized fertilizers and insecticides, and training on how to grow and maintain their cocoa trees. Better-quality cocoa beans with higher yields have resulted from this, and they can now fetch a higher price on the global market.

Cameroon ranks fourth in the world in cocoa production, closely behind Ecuador. According to figures issued by the National Cocoa Coffee Council (ONCC), Cameroon's cocoa production during the just finished 2022–2023 season saw an alarming fall of 11.2% Year-over-Year. The country's cocoa sector had a difficult year based on the output numbers, which showed a total of 262,112 tons of cocoa beans—down from 295,163 tons in the previous season.

More specifically, a lack of sectoral assistance resulted in a decline in the quality of Cameroonian cocoa.

The outcome was that Cameroonian cocoa could no longer be sold on the premium market; instead, it was offered at a lower price on the global conventional market. Due to these advancements, growing cocoa is no longer a desirable career. Several variables were identified in the ONCC's status report as contributing to the decline in cocoa production. First, part of the reason for the lower yield was the natural occurrence of the vegetative rest time in cocoa production [18]. Lower yields were also a result of farming activities being disturbed by the negative effects of climate change [20]. The security conditions in the agricultural basins of the Northwest and Southwest also presented serious difficulties, restricting access to farms and upsetting the supply chain.

The cocoa industry saw several encouraging advancements in spite of the difficulties. During the campaign, 89,204 tons of beans were processed by local cocoa processors, encompassing both industrial and artisanal units. This represents a 2.7% increase over the previous year. The cocoa production in Cameroon from 2012/2013 to 2022/2023 is depicted in the picture below.

Production of cocoa beans in Cameroon (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

The dynamic performance of the already-existing industry and the arrival of Africa Processing as a new player were credited with this expansion. Positive trends were also seen in producer pricing, which peaked at US\$ 2.6 per kilogram, a 14.7% rise over the previous year. The minimal average price per kilogram stayed at US\$1.35.

Nigeria is another significant global producer of cocoa beans, situated close to Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire. According to Statista, Nigeria is currently the fifth-largest producer of cocoa and the fourth-largest exporter of

cocoa beans worldwide. Its cocoa production is comparable to that of Cameroon. It comes in second to Ivory Coast and Ghana in terms of output share worldwide, with a range of 7% to 8%. Even though Nigeria is among the world's top 5 producers of cocoa—it only trails Ivory Coast, Ghana, Ecuador, and Cameroon—its production is still very small. Nigeria produces roughly 340,163 tons of cocoa beans annually, compared to 2,200,000 tons produced by Ivory Coast. The figure below shows the production of cocoa beans in Nigeria from the period between 2012/2013 to 2022/2023.

Production of cocoa beans in Nigeria (in 1,000 metric tons)

Source: Statista 2023

Nigeria's climate facilitates the harvest and distribution of cocoa beans from October to June. During this comparatively extended season of cocoa production, 1.4 million hectares of cropland are under cultivation. With a few commercial plantings, the 300,000–350,000 smallholder farmers in Nigeria dominate the cocoa industry. 1,400,000 hectares are farmed on average. The country's most popular export good, excluding oil, is cocoa. The processing sector in the area is expanding quickly. As a result, the industry employs more people and can produce a greater range of processed cocoa goods.

Approximately 90% of the cocoa produced in Nigeria is exported as cocoa beans, with the remaining 10% undergoing processing prior to shipment, according to the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) [16]. Although cocoa continues to be one of Nigeria's principal agricultural exports, the absence of processing facilities prevents Nigerian cocoa farmers from getting the most money for their crop. As of right now, Osun State's Ede Cocoa Processing Plant is the sole fully operational processing facility.

In overall terms, West Africa—particularly Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire—is where the great majority of the world's cocoa beans are farmed. More than 30% of the cocoa beans supplied to chocolate manufacturers like Nestlé and Mars are exported from Côte d'Ivoire alone. There is a big chocolate market worldwide. The manufacturers, who are primarily from Europe, who make chocolate bars and other confections, make enormous profits from it. The stores who stock these products on their shelves also make a ton of money from them.

More cocoa beans are exported from Côte d'Ivoire than any other country in the world. Multinational corporations dominate local processing and trading, with the majority of cocoa exported either raw or semi-processed. Approximately 25% of the population of the nation is dependent on cocoa revenue. However, these cocoa growers make a meager \$1 a day—less than the \$1.90 that represents the extreme poverty line. These farmers and their workers are the backbone of the global chocolate industry, but they only receive slightly more than 5% of the ultimate cost of a chocolate bar.

To extract greater value from this important commodity, governments and the corporate sector have been attempting to advance up the cocoa value chain. Consumer preferences that now prioritize chocolate made from beans to bars and cacao supplied ethically have aided these initiatives.

COCOA INDUSTRY'S CONTRIBUTION TO ECONOMIC GROWTH OF GULF AFRICAN COUNTRIES

The economies of the Gulf African nations that produce cocoa have booming agricultural industries that, depending on the country, contribute 14% to 40% of GDP [8]. A significant portion of the workforce in the area is employed in agriculture, particularly in the cocoa industry, which is dominated by smallholder growers who use cocoa as their main source of income. Cocoa has a major economic impact on the macroeconomic conditions of Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Cameroon, and Nigeria as well as the personal incomes of marginalized populations.

About 800,000 farming families are employed in Ghana's agriculture sector, which brings approximately \$2 billion a year in foreign exchange profits from exports. It was predicted that Ghana's cocoa industry would contribute 3.15 billion Ghanaian cedis (GHS), or about 262.8 million US dollars, to the GDP of the nation in 2023 (GDP). In 2021, the value was estimated to be 3.1 billion GHS, or around 258.6 million USD. Moreover, by 2027, agricultural output was predicted to contribute 3.75 billion GHS, or around 312.9 million US dollars, to the nation's GDP, the most amount during the examined period. Ghana produced an estimated 689,000 metric tons of cocoa beans during the 2021–2022 agricultural season.

The greatest export crop in Côte d'Ivoire, cocoa makes up 39% of the country's exports in 2019, bringing in over \$5 billion a year and supporting the employment of 6 million people along the entire value chain in addition to 600,000 farmers. But as West African cocoa is mostly marketed as a raw material, the producing nations only keep a little share of the \$45 billion worldwide cocoa market, which is projected to grow to \$61 billion by 2027. According to Customs data, 72% of

cocoa is exported from Côte d'Ivoire in the form of whole beans, compared to 68% in Ghana. The bottom end of the value chain is where most processing is concentrated, with chocolate and consumables with chocolate flavors primarily catering to the local or regional market.

The cocoa trade is highly concentrated among a limited number of companies, mostly multinational companies, in both Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire. The same is true for local processing power, even if local competitors are attempting to carve out a market share. The two governments are increasingly collaborating to affect the prices of commodities globally, and in order to bolster farmers' earnings, they introduced a living income difference (LID) in late 2019 [15]. Farmgate prices are determined centrally. Farmers' profits increased by 28% as a result of the new pricing structure being put into place for the 2020–2021 season.

The world's fourth-largest producer of cocoa is Cameroon. With an estimated 400,000 jobs created by the cocoa value chain—including 29,300 family jobs, 2,800 formal workers, 73,000 full-time equivalent workers in rural areas, and 293,000 farmers—the cocoa business is a significant job creator. Additionally, cocoa contributes significantly to state revenue. In Cameroon, the cocoa value chain adds €400 million in value added (direct + indirect), 1.2% to the country's GDP, and 8.2% to the GDP of agriculture. The cocoa value chain contributes around €37 million annually to the national budget after accounting for the €7.8 million spent on government subsidies and various programs. Recognizing the value of the cocoa industry to the country's economy, the Cameroonian government set lofty targets to double the country's cocoa production by 2030 and increase it to 600,000 MT by 2025.

Nigeria's economy has benefited greatly from the production of cocoa. Farmers won't have anything to sell in the market if there is no production. Diversification is now a reality rather than a myth. Thus, in terms of generating foreign exchange revenues, jobs, income, and food and nutritional security, agriculture is essential to our collective survival as a people. The average yearly contribution of cocoa to the nation's Gross Domestic Product is US\$313.33 million [3]. The product's contribution to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product increased by an average of 2% year between 1980 and 2017. The value of Nigeria's cocoa exports rose from 243.39 million dollars in 1980 to 598.19 million dollars in 2017, representing a significant increase in foreign exchange revenues. N122.89 billion was made from the export of raw cocoa beans and cocoa products in the first quarter of 2022. Nigerian exporters of cocoa generally ship their product directly to the United Kingdom, France, Uruguay, Germany, and the Netherlands.

In addition to being the main non-oil foreign exchange earner for Nigeria, cocoa employs millions of people in the forms of growers, processors, licensed buying agents, merchants, and exporters. With a production capacity of 340,163 tons, Nigeria is currently ranked fourth in the world for cocoa output, behind Ghana, Indonesia, and Cote d'Ivoire. It also provides roughly 41.6% to Nigeria's export revenues [17].

Nevertheless, a million or so cocoa producers in the Gulf of Africa do not make enough money to meet all of their basic need. A lot of cocoa growers only earn \$1.42 per person each day [21]. It is essential to first understand the cocoa production value chain in order to comprehend why upstream cocoa producers receive such low wages. Upstream cocoa farmers are the lowest paid and lowest level of the five levels, with sourcing and marketing coming in at level two. This group consists of both domestic and international buying agents (such as exporters and cocoa traders) who export both raw and semi-finished cocoa beans. The companies that process the beans (manufacturers, grinders, etc.) are ranked third on the value chain. Distributors, which include retailers, come in fourth. The consumers live at the last level downstream.

Since retailers, manufacturers, and other intermediaries have taken a larger share of the value chain each year, cocoa farmers upstream—who are at the bottom of the totem pole—have increasingly fetched lower prices. As a result, the value of cocoa beans has decreased from 50% of a chocolate bar in the 1970s to less than 6% today.

The governments of Ivory Coast and Ghana made an effort in 2019 to protect their farmers from poverty by introducing a Living Income Differential, which increased farmer incomes by \$400 per ton of cocoa. However, many large chocolate producers, such as Mondelez and Nestle, have been taking advantage of poor farmers for decades by deftly evading these regulations and paying extremely low prices for raw cocoa beans[5].

CONCLUSION

Agriculture in the Gulf African countries is changing. The most favorable conditions for agricultural growth in more than 30 years have been created by a confluence of factors including robust demand growth, steady economic expansion, rising global agriculture prices, and better policy environments. Now more than ever, the Gulf African countries and their Development Partners understand how critical the industry is to overall economic growth, food security, better nutrition, and the fight against poverty.

Ivory Coast, Ghana, Cameroon, Nigeria, and other African nations that produce cocoa have benefited greatly from cocoa production, which creates jobs and opens up export markets. As a result, cocoa is a valuable agricultural export commodity with significant investment and export potential. It can be used to make a variety of manufactured and semi-manufactured goods, including chocolates, cosmetics, cocoa butter, cocoa cake, and cocoa powder, which can all be used to generate diversified foreign exchange revenue. In addition to being a vital raw material for regional businesses, cocoa and cocoa-based goods have a stable market throughout the world.

Despite market trends indicating rising worldwide demand for cocoa, the African cocoa business faces a number of obstacles. Among the numerous hurdles, the abundance of pests, illnesses, and changeable weather continue to limit the market's potential.

Aside from the challenges, value-added operations like as grinding and processing are primarily carried out in Europe, which accounts for around 77% of cocoa

grinding. The Netherlands and Germany are the leading cocoa-grinding countries, accounting for 62.5% of European capacity. Outside of Africa, consumption is also concentrated, with Europe and the Americas accounting for 77% of consumption at 45% and 32%, respectively.

Contrast that with the combined US\$7 billion earned by the world's two largest cocoa producers, Ivory Coast and Ghana, in 2019/2020. These two cocoa production industry heavyweights generated more than 65% of all worldwide cocoa in 2019, but only receive 5% of the actual value of the final chocolate product in 2019-2020. One key explanation for the large disparity in worldwide chocolate revenue between Europe and Africa is that the latter is at the bottom of the value chain, with its function limited to raw material production and export. In contrast, Europe processes the majority of this raw material, turns it into chocolate, and sells it to customers. Africa is aiming to climb up the cocoa value chain by constructing cocoa processing plants and providing financial incentives to private enterprises to do the same. However, it is insufficient to make a significant impact on the global market.

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